

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies / IPBES transformative change assessment (4.3)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address a wide range of challenges and obstacles that impede transformative change toward a sustainable world for nature and people, with a focus on strategies to overcome them in order to advance global, regional and local visions for a sustainable world for nature and people. The chapter provides evidence on challenges associated with policy development, implementation and coherence, including representation and consideration of conflicting worldviews and visions, coupling of policy processes, lock-in effects and path dependencies, unintended policy consequences and inequality. In this context, a review of literature focused on institutional misfits and inadequate policies was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

The evidence for section 4.2.3 was gathered through five searches to which the same screening criteria was applied to examine the challenges regarding institutional misfits and inadequate policies. Indeed, after having identified and read closely the selected papers from the first process, experts realized that some key papers were not captured by the search, which this resulted in conducting additional searches to complement the selected papers and to better ground in the literature the challenges identified in analysing the 53 selected papers from the starting search.

Process 1 – Systematic academic literature search based on keywords on biodiversity, ecosystem services, governance, institutions and misfits

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based systematic literature review
- **Search terms:**

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY((biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem*) AND (institution* OR policy OR rule*) AND (misfit OR unfit OR misalignment)) AND (EXCLUDE(DOCTYPE, "cp") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE, "ch") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE, "bk")) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "COMP") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "NURS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "MATE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "PHAR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "CENG"))
```
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Date:** 21February 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 249 records **(A)**
- **Treatment applied:** Initial screening excluded books, book chapters, conference papers, medical, business, computer science, electronics and chemical engineering papers, leading to a result of 197 records **(B)**.

TITLE-ABS-KEY((biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem*) AND (institution* OR policy OR rule*) AND (misfit OR unfit OR misalignment)) AND (EXCLUDE(DOCTYPE, "cp") OR EXCLUDE(DOCTYPE, "ch") OR EXCLUDE(DOCTYPE, "bk")) AND (EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "COMP") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "NURS") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "MATE") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "PHAR") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "CENG"))

Figure 1. Illustration of results on Scopus for search 1.

- **Treatment applied:** A second screening was applied using the following criteria:
 - **Abstract reading and screening**
 - **exclude (i.e., mark as red) if:**
 - Paper address issues of biodiversity/ecosystems but it is not about institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits but does not relate with biodiversity/nature/environmental issues
 - **include (green) only if:**
 - Paper address issues of biodiversity/ecosystems AND discuss institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits RELATED TO biodiversity/nature/environmental issues
 - **yellow if:**
 - Paper address issues of biodiversity/ecosystems AND discuss institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness AND discusses ways to overcome institutional/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits RELATED TO biodiversity/nature/environmental issues AND discusses ways to overcome institutional/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
- **Sample extracted:** 53 relevant records (C).

Process 2: Systematic academic literature search based on keywords on institutional fit and spatial fit

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based systematic literature review
- **Search terms:**

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( ( biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem* OR environment ) AND ( "institutional fit" OR "spatial fit" ) ) )
```

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Date:** March 8, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 73 records (**D**)
- **Treatment applied:** Records related to informatics, chemistry, astronomy, higher education, marketing, business administration and human resource management were filtered out. Two screenings were then applied based on specific criteria (**R1**).
- **Sample extracted:** 27 records (**E**)
- **Treatment applied:** After a second, more in-depth screen run using the same criteria, those 27 were brought down to 5 records (**F**) (after reading the pieces in more detail, beyond the abstract).

Details search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based systematic literature review
- **Search terms:**

```
fit AND social-ecological
```

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Date:** March 8, 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 90 000 records
- **Treatment applied:** the first 50 records (**G**) were screened based on specific criteria (**R1**).
- **Sample extracted:** 10 records (**H**)

Process 3: Systematic academic literature search based on keywords on biodiversity, institutions, policy and governance

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based systematic literature review
- **Search terms:**

```
( ( biodiversity OR nature OR environment OR ecosystem* OR ecological OR biosphere OR earth ) AND ( institution* OR social OR policy OR rule* OR institutional AND architectures ) AND ( misfit OR unfit OR misalignment ) )
```

- **Search languages:** English
 - **Search engine:** Semantic Scholar
 - **Sample extracted:** 1 record.
-

Process 4: Search based on questions used on Elicit.org

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** question-based review
- **Search terms:**

```
What are the examples of institutional misfit in biodiversity conservation?
```

- **Search languages:** English
 - **Search engine:** Elicit
 - **Sample extracted:** 27 records
-

Process 5: Review of grey literature

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based review of grey literature
- **Search terms:**

```
Institution, biodiversity, governance
```

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google
- **Sample extracted:** 7 records (J)
- **Treatment applied:** viewed literature published after 2015 and excluded academic journal articles. Many documents were hit, so only extracted literature that was relevant to the chapter was extracted, by checking the content. The aim was to see what trends exist in the grey literature. As a result, there was a limited amount of relevant literature.

Details search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based review of grey literature
- **Search terms:**

(biodiversity AND nature AND environment* AND ecosystem* OR ecological OR biosphere OR earth) AND (institution* OR social OR policy rule* institutional architectures) AND (misfit AND unfit AND misalignment AND problems of fit) AND (challenges barrier* OR obstacle* OR hurdle*) AND (governing AND law regulation*) AND (solutions OR innovations) AND (economic OR financial)

- **Search languages:** English
- **Date:** May 18, 2023
- **Search engine:** Harvard Kennedy School Think Tank
- **Sample extracted:** 1 record (**J**)

Details search 3:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based review of grey literature
- **Search terms:**

(biodiversity AND nature AND environment* AND ecosystem* OR ecological OR biosphere OR earth) AND (institution* OR social OR policy AND rule* AND institutional architectures) AND (misfit AND unfit AND misalignment AND problems AND of AND fit)

- **Search languages:** English
- **Date:** May 18, 2023
- **Search engine:** Harvard Kennedy School Think Tank
- **Sample extracted:** 2 records
- **Treatment applied:** 1 book of symposium abstract excluded, 1 article selected as relevant (**J**).

Details search 4:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based review of grey literature
- **Search terms:**

((biodiversity OR nature OR environment OR ecosystem* OR ecological OR biosphere OR earth) AND (institution* OR social OR policy OR rule* OR institutional AND architectures) AND (misfit OR unfit OR misalignment))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Date:** May 18, 2023
- **Search engine:** Harvard Kennedy School Think Tank
- **Sample extracted:** 8 180 000 records
- **Treatment applied:** 10 first results were screened. 1 article was selected as relevant – the rest were unrelated to biodiversity, ecosystems or nature conservation (**J**).

Details search 5:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** keyword-based review of grey literature

- **Search terms:**

((biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem*) AND (institution* OR policy OR rule*) AND (misfit OR unfit OR misalignment))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Date:** May 18, 2023
- **Search engine:** Harvard Kennedy School Think Tank
- **Sample extracted:** 34 500 000 records
- **Treatment applied:** 10 first results were screened; all were excluded as they were unrelated to biodiversity, ecosystems or nature conservation (**J**).

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(A)	CSV	472 KB	249 records from systematic academic literature search based on keywords on biodiversity, ecosystem services, governance, institutions and misfits
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(B)	CSV	447 KB	197 records selected from systematic academic literature search based on keywords on biodiversity, ecosystem services, governance, institutions and misfits
C	3_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(C)	CSV	114	53 relevant records from systematic academic literature search based on keywords on biodiversity, ecosystem services, governance, institutions and misfits
D	4_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(D)	PDF	186 KB	73 records extracted from search 1 on institutional fit and spatial fit
E	5_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(E)	PDF	161 KB	27 records selected from search 1 on institutional fit and spatial fit
F	6_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(F)	PDF	149 KB	5 relevant records from search 1 on institutional fit and spatial fit
G	7_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(G)	PDF	147 KB	First 50 records in search 2 on institutional fit and spatial fit
H	8_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(H)	PDF	125 KB	10 relevant records selected in search 2 on institutional fit and spatial fit
R1	9_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(R1)	PDF	147 KB	Screening rules applied for both searches on institutional fit and spatial fit
J	10_IPBES_TCA_DMR 4.3_11-2024_(J)	PDF	108 KB	Relevant articles selected from review of grey literature